

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS WITH PRESSURE ACTUATED LEAF SEALS FOR
SUPERHEATED STEAM TURBINE APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Modern load-follow operation of powerplants and turbines requires new sealing technologies for both flexible and efficient long-term operability. Those with radial adaptivity such as Pressure Actuated Leaf Seals (PALS) have high potential to fulfil these requirements even if series maturity is not given yet.

In this paper, multiple preliminary investigations with industry-oriented designed PALS at a compressed-air test rig at TU Braunschweig are presented. The experiments, which should prepare hot steam tests with very similar seals, were performed without rotation of the shaft disc but instead with five different shaft diameters as well as eccentrically shifted.

The results show a very strong correlation between geometric clearance and leakage behaviour. It could be proven that a slight overlap of the pressurised seal inner diameter and shaft can realise a distinct global leakage minimum at significant differential pressure. But even a tiny clear gap remaining when the leaves are fully deflected can more than double the design leakage with an overlapping configuration. Evidence for good eccentricity tolerance within the clear gap are given as well as for high-frequency oscillation propensity under low pressure and clearance conditions.

This challenge, the wear reliability and operation behaviour depending on the rotational speed have to be addressed in future experiments.

Keywords: Radially Adaptive Seal, Steam Turbine, Seal Aerodynamics, Compressed Air Experiments, Seal Oscillations

Q	$\sqrt{\text{kgK/J}}$	flow function
r	mm	radius
R_S	J/kgK	specific gas constant
t	ms	time
T	ms	period
T	K	temperature (static)
γ	-	heat capacity ratio
Δ	-	difference
Π	-	pressure ratio

Subscript

1	upstream
2	downstream
air	air
C	contact (pressure)
crit	critical
D	design (pressure)
eff	effective (clearance)
g	geometric (clearance)
max	maximum
ref	reference
rel	relative

Abbreviations

IFAS	Institute of Jet Propulsion and Turbomachinery
PALS	Pressure Actuated Leaf Seal
SD	shaft disc

NOMENCLATURE

c	mm	seal clearance
d	mm	diameter
e	mm	eccentricity
\dot{m}	g/s	leakage mass flow
p	bar	pressure (static)

1. INTRODUCTION

The strong increase in volatility of energy and, especially, electricity generation worldwide has massively changed the range of applications and thus the load and operating behaviour of conventional power plants in general and stationary steam turbines in particular. While these were traditionally used mainly

to cover the base load, for example in nuclear or coal-fired power plants, and thus operated predominantly at full load, by now they are increasingly used to compensate peak loads caused by solar and wind energy. This so-called load-follow operation implies frequent start-up and shutdown processes, load ramps and longer partial load operation. [1]

The changed application scenarios also directly entail correspondingly different design boundary conditions for the respective turbines. The optimisation of efficiency, which has been economically and ecologically imperative for decades, must indeed be continued. But according to the new operational environment it follows that, in addition to stationary (full-load) operation, the load-switching capability and the quick-start behaviour of the turbines must also be addressed in particular. Against the background of this being always accompanied by a comparatively poorer running smoothness of the machines - vibrations and eccentricities of the shaft occur more frequently [2] – a conflict of objectives arises here with conventional sealing technologies. These, which include labyrinth seals in particular, usually have as their most important design parameter the radial gap height or clearance, which must be minimised as far as possible. If low-wear and operational reliability are now introduced as necessary boundary conditions even for the modern, challenging application scenarios, the targeted increases in efficiency are no longer possible.

Radially adaptive sealing systems such as Pressure Actuated Leaf Seals (PALS), which were developed for sealing between turbine stages, provide a remedy here. Such seals, which have variable radial gap heights depending on the operating point, can thus realise wear resistance during load changes on the one hand and low leakage at full load on the other. [3] In this context, the main parameters influencing the operating behaviour of PALS are analysed experimentally in this paper. The focus is on seals for large shaft diameters suitable for use in stationary steam turbines.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter introduces both the technology of PALS and the analysed seal as well as the compressed air test rig used with its metrology and measurement uncertainties. It is then completed by a short overview of the test campaign.

2.1 PALS Technology

Pressure Actuated Leaf Seals are a type of radially adaptive seals designed for turbine stage separation between rotor and stator [3]. The basic principle and construction are shown in Fig. 1. The radial adaptivity is realised by two layers of metal leaves which stand circumferentially staggered so that there is only a clear gap between the leaf tips and the shaft. While PALS were introduced as a non-contacting seal during operation, it is important to state that a wear-in at initial operation can be accepted on purpose in order to minimise the clearance during long-term operation [3]. Beside the leaf seal elements PALS can be composed of several other components that should improve the operational behaviour such as a support member. Its function is to sustain the leaves under pressure and at the same time to

avoid oscillations. Also, the seal envelope can be constructed in different ways depending on boundary conditions of the specific application. In contrast to e. g. brush seals, PALS are constructed independently of the direction of shaft rotation.

FIGURE 1: BASIC STRUCTURE AND WORKING PRINCIPLE OF PRESSURE ACTUATED LEAF SEALS (PALS) [3]

2.2 Test Seal

The nominal seal test rig shaft diameter at the Institute of Jet Propulsion and Turbomachinery (IFAS) is $\varnothing 300$ mm. This includes two air test rigs as well as a hot steam test rig for later industry-oriented experiments. Therefore, this is also the design diameter of the present test seal that was specially manufactured for these experiments and test rig boundary conditions. Its leaves are depicted as a segment photographed from the inside out in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2: SEGMENT OF THE ANALYSED PALS – RADIAL VIEW ONTO THE LEAVES FROM THE INSIDE OUT

The nominal or design pressure difference amounts to $\Delta p_D = 25$ bar, whereby the maximum deflection of the leaves is already reached at approximately $\Delta p_C = 6.9$ bar (100 psid). At this so-called contact pressure p_C , which is one of the most important PALS design parameters, the bottom leaves are fully in contact with the support member or backing ring which are one and the same component here. The backing ring has an inner diameter of $\varnothing 302.02$ mm and an angle of around 45° to the rotating axis. Its frontside is formed slightly convex so that the contact zone with the bottom leaves is increasing continuously with the applied pressure difference.

The inner diameter of the seal/leaves was manufactured to $\varnothing 299.745$ mm while the leaves were fully deflected. According to the calculated design, which is basically suitable for

superheated steam operation at the IFAS test rig, too, the radial deflection is 0.579 mm at Δp_c . This leads to an inner diameter of $\text{Ø}300.903$ mm pressureless. Furthermore, a slight radial overlap with the shaft of approximately 0.128 mm is given. This idea has already been presented and subjected to initial tests, but with a significantly smaller shaft diameter. [4]

Lastly, the test seal is composed of two leaf layers with 120 leaves each. At the same time, the front leaves are a little bit wider, but also thinner than the back leaves that should primarily support the front leaves and cover the very narrow interspace between them. This is also well discernible in Fig. 2. The materials used are heat-resistant Inconel X-750 (all leaves) and stainless steel type 304/304L (both front- and backplate).

2.3 Test Rig and Equipment

For the purpose of understanding the operating behaviour of seals in general or PALS in particular, two compressed air test rigs are available at IFAS. The tests shown here were carried out on the test rig with the shaft disc stationary, i. e. without any shaft rotation. Fig. 3 gives an overview of all test rig components.

FIGURE 3: STATIONARY SEAL TEST RIG WITH COMPRESSED AIR AT IFAS, TU BRAUNSCHWEIG

After passing the measurement sites for volume flow (1), static pressure (2) and temperature (3) as well as the control valve (4), the compressed air flows through the bearing case (5) into the seal rack (6) which is assembled in a concentric way around the shaft disc that is held by an own fixture (7). The locking device (8) allows to lock the seal rack at 24 certain circumferential positions while the notch (9) gives optical access to the seal rack and the gap system. The compressed air is cooled down and dried to more or less constant standard conditions before entering the test rig and escapes to the ambient after the seal rack again. The maximum air parameters are about 220 g/s mass flow at a pressure of up to 8 bar(a).

In addition to the measurement of the leakage this setup enables optical observations of the adaptive sealing leaves during operation. These observations can be performed by means of two different digital microscopes: one for stationary colour images and another for high-speed monochrome videos, both with lenses with up to 200x optical zoom. Using differently

designed shaft discs, either the clear radial gap can be measured precisely or the axial behaviour of the seal can be analysed in more detail by observing radially out of the running surface as depicted in Fig. 4 (A and B).

FIGURE 4: TEST SETUPS A/B FOR TWO-SIDED OPTICAL ACCESS TO SEAL GAP SYSTEM AT TEST RIG NOTCH

The two-sided optical access to the gap system also allows impressions of transient phenomena at the leaves. Only these measurements and analyses provide a comprehensive overall picture of the seal performance in practical application, e.g. in a turbine.

For more detailed information about the test rigs, which have already been used in the past for extensive experiments with different types of brush seals, see also [5], [6], [7].

2.4 Metrology and Measurement Uncertainties

All air parameters are measured globally within the line – as Fig. 3 (1-3) shows – or within the high-pressure chamber at the front side of the shaft disc. Locally resolved measurements are not possible at this setup. The leakage mass flow is calculated by the volume flow and the air density determined by pressure and temperature. Therefore, its measurement uncertainty must be calculated in an equivalent way. Tab. 1 shows the calculated uncertainties for the pressure measurement:

TABLE 1: UNCERTAINTIES OF PRESSURE MEASUREMENTS AT DIFFERENT STATIC PRESSURE LEVELS

Δp bar	Systematic Uncertainty %
1	± 1.0
2	± 0.5
3	± 0.33
4	± 0.25
5	± 0.2
6	± 0.17
7	± 0.14

While the thermocouple type K used in the line has a constant absolute uncertainty of ± 2 K, the swirl volume flow meter has a constant relative uncertainty of ± 0.5 % within the whole measuring range. Taking these values as a reference, the systematic uncertainty of the mass flow measuring at a constant

line pressure of about 7.2 bar amounts to ca. $\pm 0.95\%$. Further uncertainties due to electrical transfer resistors at the measuring chain are small and can be ignored.

The radial gap height or clearance between leaf tips and shaft disc surface is measured by means of the stationary digital microscope. The photos, here standardised taken with 20x optical zoom, can be measured by the corresponding communication software. These measurements have a maximum accuracy of 5 pixels. Together with a width of $3.24\ \mu\text{m}$ per pixel at 20x zoom, the resulting uncertainty amounts to around $16.2\ \mu\text{m}$.

Additionally, for high-speed recordings, the other microscope was on hand. Its software allows to analyse periodic motion within the monochrome videos. With the frame rate of 15,000 fps used, frequencies in the lower kilohertz range can be determined with good accuracy.

2.5 Test Campaign

The test seal was analysed with multiple stationary shaft disc diameters in order to deeply understand its behaviour at varying clearances. Thus, after the measurement of every characteristic, the shaft disc is lathed to the next smaller diameter. For these tests, the experimental setup in Fig. 4A was used with the shaft disc newly centred to the seal rack after every reworking. Tab. 2 specifies the analysed shaft disc diameters and the theoretical radial overlap respectively gap with fully deflected leaves (the numbers will be used throughout the paper):

TABLE 2: SHAFT DISC DIAMETERS TESTED AND THEIR NOMINAL RADIAL GAP/OVERLAP WITH THE LEAVES AT Δp_c

No.	SD Diameter d mm	Radial Gap/Overlap at Δp_c mm
I	299.88	-0.0675
II	299.70	0.0225
III	299.61	0.0675
IV	299.52	0.1125
V	299.42	0.1625

At the end, the shaft disc with $\varnothing 299.88\ \text{mm}$ (SD I) was also used for a stationary eccentricity test with the shaft disc radially shifted to the seal by about $0.1\ \text{mm}$. For each of the tests, both a geometric radial clearance closing characteristic and a leakage mass flow characteristic were measured. The latter is primarily depicted in this paper by the effective clearance as per Eqs. (1) and (2) [8]:

$$c_{eff} = \dot{m} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{T_1}}{2\pi r \cdot p_1 \cdot Q} \quad (1)$$

$$Q = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{R_s(\gamma-1)} \left[\left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right)^{\frac{2}{\gamma}} - \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma}} \right]} & \text{if } \frac{p_1}{p_2} \leq \left(\frac{\gamma+1}{2}\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \\ \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{R_s} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{\gamma+1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{\gamma-1}}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In these equations, the variable Q is the flow function of ideal, isentropic nozzle flow. It is calculated as an annulus and related to the measured leakage and ambient conditions.

Among others, Gaszner et al. [9] and Crudgington [10] have used this formulation of de Saint Venant's equation after Trutnovsky and Komotori [8] for different annular seal performance descriptions. The advantage of this normalised definition is that the ambient conditions are subtracted out so that measurements become comparable even with other seals, seal types or test rigs.

Every characteristic consists of measurements at differential pressure levels from 0 bar up to Δp_{max} in steps of 0.2 bar each. Some steps were skipped for cost reasons if no important result was expected. The particular Δp_{max} of a characteristic is limited by the maximum available compressed-air mass flow. Every single pressure stage was tested stationary at 24 circumferential positions of the seal rack and averaged afterwards. By doing so, possible circumferential disparities, especially of the radial clearance measured, could be eliminated.

Some further observations were made with the Fig. 4B setup afterwards. The aim was to understand the leaf movement better even if the shaft disc with the acrylic glass mirror segment has a slightly other diameter than the clearance variation discs.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Basic Operation Behaviour

Standardly, a PALS characteristic is drawn as a function of the leakage mass flow or effective clearance over the current differential pressure over the seal respectively its leaves. In Fig. 5, this is plotted for the entire clearance variation of the tested seal, i. e. with all available shaft disc diameters in this test campaign (SD I-V).

FIGURE 5: EFFECTIVE CLEARANCE AFTER EQ. (1) SUBJECT TO THE DIFFERENTIAL SEAL PRESSURE FOR SEVERAL SHAFT DISC DIAMETERS

It is apparent that there is a clear coincidence between the radial clearance or the shaft disc diameter and the leakage so that the characteristics are lying one above another. The lowest of them derives from SD I, whose diameter is next to the design diameter of $\varnothing 300\ \text{mm}$. It still has a slight overlap between the shaft disc and the leaves when theoretically fully deflected. The maximum leaf deflection with full shaft surface contact is reached at around 3.5 bar here. This leads to a kind of an asymptotic value of 0.08 for the standardised effective clearance. This leakage presumably mostly flows through the small but

unavoidable interleaf gaps. The same effect has also been investigated for brush seals with a similar fence height (radial distance between deflected leaf/bristle tip and backplate inner diameter) of about 1.0 mm already [11]. It is important to put on record that the leaves cannot get fully in contact with the backplate with this shaft disc diameter since the shaft contact is reached at $\Delta p < \Delta p_c$. This might have slightly increased the asymptotic interleaf leakage compared to other operating points.

At this point it is helpful to have a look at the geometric clearance characteristics depicted in Fig. 6 as well.

FIGURE 6: GEOMETRICAL RADIAL CLEARANCE SUBJECT TO THE DIFFERENTIAL SEAL PRESSURE FOR SEVERAL SHAFT DISC DIAMETERS

When having a look at the corresponding geometric radial clearance characteristic for SD I, it becomes apparent that the gap between leaf tips and shaft is indeed completely closed as from around 3.5 bar. Basically, at low pressure differences with a large clearance, the effective clearance will always be smaller than the geometrical clearance due to the effect of jet contraction at a sharp-edged nozzle. In these cases, the interleaf flow is relatively negligibly. But the more the leaves are deflected, the more the interleaf flow is superimposing the non-isentropic jet contraction so that the effective clearance can even be higher than the geometrical. Consequently, the slope of the geometrical characteristic will always be higher than of the effective one.

The full deflection to the backplate contact pressure can only be reached with the next smaller SD II. With a diameter of $\varnothing 299.70$ mm its cold radial clearance to the seal should be 0.09 mm higher than before. This gap is large enough for the full deflection of 0.579 mm predicted for Δp_c . But it is also small enough so that the design contact pressure of 6.9 bar can almost be reached with the available compressed-air mass flow at the test rig. With the resulting stable $\Delta p_{max} = 6.0$ bar, the radial deflection of the leaves amounts to 0.49 mm. This is slightly less than numerically predicted by the manufacturer even if considering the difference between Δp_c and Δp_{max} . As a result, this deflection characteristic is almost covering the whole nominal deflection of the seal.

With respect to Fig. 5 it can be shown that even this small increase of the clear gap height of less than 0.1 mm at higher differential pressures more than doubles the leakage (from 0.08 to 0.216 asymptotic effective clearance, standardised). Thus, it is strongly indicated that an overlapping design with initial wear-

in could be very important for a high-efficient PALS design. This is especially weighing since higher pressure differences will still be more industrially relevant. At the same time, at low-pressure points, the effective clearance rises less than the geometrical clearance due to jet contraction.

Further reducing the shaft disc diameter by 0.1 mm to $\varnothing 299.61$ mm (SD III), the effective clearance is exactly rising by another 0.1 over the whole pressure range. This is the case even if the first shaft diameter reduction was by 0.16 mm which means that an increase of the clearance is more harmful at higher clearances. Vice versa, it seems like clearance reduction has a degressive influence on the seal leakage so that a slightly overlapping, but also conservative seal design could often be suitable. The maximal differential pressure at this shaft diameter (5.6 bar) also almost reaches the asymptotic range of the clearance characteristics so that the leaf deflection aggregates to 0.48 mm.

Although, due to the compressor capacity of the test rig, the characteristics are not complete anymore, the two more steps of shaft disc diameter reduction (SD IV and V, $\varnothing 299.52$ mm and $\varnothing 299.42$ mm) show similar leakage behaviour up to their specific Δp_{max} – see Fig. 5. With differences of about 0.06 standardised effective clearance each, a constant percentage of the geometrical gap enlargement results in leakage increase. Indeed, there was a technical problem with measuring the geometrical clearance so that the geometric closing characteristics of SD IV and V could not be ascertained correctly. However, the total radial deflection up to the specific Δp_{max} could still be measured: For SD V, it amounts to 0.45 mm despite the very low maximum pressure difference applicable (3.2 bar), which indicates that the leaf design is relatively soft here.

In general, it is noticeable that the geometric closing characteristic of the seal is strongly degressive. This behaviour is determined by the convex backplate contour. Thus, the free length of the cantilever that the leaves physically represent, gets shorter and shorter with increasing leaf deflection by successively raising contact zones.

In addition to the described standardised leakage characteristics, it is remarkable that PALS have the ability to even reduce the absolute leakage with increasing differential pressure. These mass flow characteristics are plotted in Fig. 7.

FIGURE 7: ABSOLUTE LEAKAGE MASS FLOW SUBJECT TO THE DIFFERENTIAL SEAL PRESSURE FOR SEVERAL SHAFT DISC DIAMETERS

This phenomenon, which might be very interesting in order to estimate total leakage losses in industrial application, only occurs at small clearances next to the overlapping design geometry: With SD I, a distinct local leakage maximum of 0.318 standardised is found at 0.6-0.8 bar. Starting from this point, the leakage decreases by 37 % as far as 0.2 when leaf tips get fully in contact with the shaft. Since there is no further geometric deflection anymore, at this state the global leakage minimum is formed. Up from there, under constant geometric conditions, the leakage has a quite linear slope as a subject to the differential pressure – a plausible behaviour for supercritical pressure ratios ($\Pi_{crit,air} = 0.528$). Extrapolating this, it would be expected that the 0.2-bar leakage maximum is not reached again until about 7.6 bar differential pressure. The slight increase at very low differential pressures (0.2-0.4 bar) in defiance of the steep geometric closing characteristic at this state can be referred to predominant compressibility effects of the air.

Such a strong leakage-controlling behaviour is not common for other seals, neither for also radially adaptive brush seals, as tested leakage characteristics for different brush seal configurations at the same test rig show [11]. For PALS designs with a remaining clear gap at Δp_c the effect disappears, too. Accidentally, the SD II diameter is almost exactly the threshold at which the local leakage minimum degenerates to a saddle point of about 1.0 bar width. For even higher clearances, the leakage-defining clear gap height eclipses the leakage reduction by radial leaf deflection. At the same time, the linear course of the curve is beginning earlier.

Summarising, on the one hand the results confirm the outstanding importance of the geometric clearance for the performance or leakage quantity of the seal. This effect could be quantified for a large gap height interval.

On the other hand, the radial deflection of the leaves can limit the circular-nozzle-flow-normalised effective clearance so that the latter monotonically decreases over the entire measured differential pressure range of 0-7 bar and thereby follows the deflection of the leaves with a lower slope. The real mass flow also has a pronounced minimum in the design case with very small clearance, which is at significant pressure differences (about 3.4-3.6 bar).

3.2 Unsteady Behaviour at Low Pressure

At some operation points, transient effects in the form of very loud tones (like screech) were found. It became clear that this was only the case under certain conditions: The tone could only be generated with the largest shaft disc (SD I) so that there was a small clearance pressureless. At the same time, the leaf pressure difference had to be small: The noise only occurred at small differential pressures of mostly 0.2 bar, rarely 0.4 bar when the geometrical clearance was between 0.2 and 0.3 mm. Optical observations by the high-speed microscope proved that the reason for the noise were high-frequency leaf oscillations. Fig. 8 shows the state when the leaves are most open during those oscillations as a freeze image taken in a radial direction of sight after the setup of Fig. 4A.

FIGURE 8: FREEZE IMAGE OF LARGEST GAP DURING LEAF OSCILLATIONS AT 0.2 BAR – AXIAL VIEW AFTER SETUP A

Indeed, it was not possible to exactly measure the amplitude of the oscillations. Presumably, compared to other measurements, it roughly amounts to 0.2 mm. Nevertheless, it is visible that the top leaf opening is wider than the one of the bottom leaves. In addition to that, a vertical motion curve of the oscillations could be measured, which is depicted in an amplitude-scaled way in Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9: SECTION OF AN OPTICALLY MEASURED MOTION CURVE OF LEAF OSCILLATIONS AT 0.2 BAR

In this case, the higher maxima represent the state when the leaves are most open like in Fig. 8 while the lower ones express the leaves being most deflected. On the basis of that, the oscillation frequency could be calculated to around 1.2 kHz and furthermore be made plausible by an additional acoustic measurement by a smartphone app. Despite several attempts, the phenomenon was not reliably reproducible so that more detailed experiments could not be conducted. Therefore, just several qualitative understandings were found:

- leaf oscillations can occur spontaneously
- there is a resulting Δp while leaves are oscillating (in this case about 0.36 bar)
- opening the control valve does not affect the seal Δp
- opening the valve raises the oscillation frequency
- very high pressure or shutdown terminates oscillation
- one time the oscillations spontaneously stopped

The root cause analysis was done by axial photographs with the shaft disc setup B, cf. Fig. 4. Those photos proved that at these low-pressure operating points the two superimposed rows of leaves are not fully in contact yet, which is visible at Fig. 10.

The microscope measurement revealed an axial gap of about 0.5 mm between the leaf tips at 0.2 bar while this gap was already reduced to 0.2 mm at 0.4 bar. At higher differential pressures, the leaf rows always move completely synchronously when further deflected. Thus, it can be assumed, that the interleaf

gap is fully closed then except for unavoidable manufacturing or material uncertainties. Due to the inclination angle of the leaves, more precise measurements are not possible at this point.

FIGURE 10: LEAF TIPS FROM BELOW AT 0.2 BAR – RADIAL VIEW OUT OF THE SHAFT DISC AFTER SETUP B

This result is entirely in accordance with existing experiments that have shown that such interleaf flow can cause high-frequent leaf vibrations [4]. Apparently, at higher pressure with more leaf layer contact, the damping is sufficient to avoid further vibration.

In any case, it is important to further understand the oscillation propensity of any PALS design before using it in an industrial context. It must be made sure that the oscillations either do not appear or can be stopped soon during operation so that they cannot damage the leaves or compromise the seal performance.

3.3 High Pressure Behaviour

When recording the measurements for high pressure with the largest shaft disc and contact between the leaves and the shaft disc running surface, significantly high torsional moments were detected when rotating the seal rack manually into the next circumferential position. The torque is obviously caused by the normal force of the leaves on the shaft disc running surface. It successively increases with the rise of the differential pressure from that moment on when the leaves are fully deflected onto the disc surface.

In preparation of later experiments at the rotating air test rig and the hot steam test rig, it was tried to get a quantitative idea of the dimension of the torque. For this purpose, selected seal rack turns were made with a dynamometer with a measuring range of up to 20 kg. The displayed forces indicated that the torque could be higher than 50 Nm at maximum Δp (ca. 7.0 bar) even if bearing friction is subtracted out. Against this background, it is very important to adjust a seal design to maximally tolerable frictional torques.

Additionally, slight scratch marks were visible at the shaft disc after disassembly. Further experiments on this topic must be performed as well so that damages at both shaft and leaves can be avoided during sufficiently long operation periods.

3.4 Eccentric Behaviour

For a deeper seal understanding and comparison purposes with other seals, SD I was used for an additional eccentricity test after the clearance variation. The adjacent Fig. 11 shows the results of this measurement in terms of the effective clearance.

FIGURE 11: EFFECTIVE CLEARANCE AFTER EQ. (1) SUBJECT TO THE DIFFERENTIAL SEAL PRESSURE AT ECCENTRIC SHAFT DISC POSITION ($e \approx 0.1$ mm)

Beside the effective clearance characteristic of SD I, which was already discussed in chapter 3.1, another characteristic for the same shaft disc, but eccentrically displaced, is plotted. The eccentricity of the shaft disc surface was determined to about 0.1 mm by means of a gauge indicator fixed at the seal rack.

It is obvious that the characteristics perfectly match each other up to 1.5 bar differential pressure. After Fig. 6, this is approximately the pressure at which the geometrical clearance amounts to 0.1 mm, too. This means that the slight eccentricity of the shaft does not have any influence on the leakage as long as it is less than the current clear gap. Afterwards, beginning at the leaf position which the shaft is shifted to, the leaves are more and more prevented from deflecting with the applied pressure difference. This then causes a higher leakage due to a larger perfused gap area. In this case, at the other side of the seal, a clear crescent moon remains even at Δp_{max} . This is conclusively discernible by the asymptotic effective clearance in this configuration, which is more than 50 % higher than in centred shaft disc position.

By this finding, the PALS is behaving qualitatively similar to straight-through labyrinth seals: Matthias and Willinger [12] have analysed that shaft eccentricity is generally increasing the leakage of this labyrinth seal type which, with one fin, can be seen as the geometrical pendant to PALS. Their result is congruent with older studies performed by Leeb [13]. The latter, however, has also proven that under certain conditions with low relative eccentricity $e_{rel} = \frac{e}{c_g} < 0.5$ the leakage needs not be eccentricity-affected at all [13]. This would be in accord with the present analysis.

3.5 Discussion and Outlook

Trying to evaluate the results presented, it has to be stated that now the basic design idea of PALS could be confirmed by the experiments also for a larger, industrially relevant shaft diameter in preparation for later hot steam application. Thereby, especially clear gaps at the PALS design become really expensive with respect to leakage and turbine efficiency. This effect becomes stronger the higher the differential pressure across the seal is, i. e. the more industrially relevant the operating point tends to be. When avoiding those clearances by extremely small radial clearance, it is still absolutely relevant to focus on the contact behaviour between seal and shaft. The question of the maximally tolerable wear-in must probably be answered in every

single application case – depending on multiple boundary conditions like heat input into the system. At once, the interoperation of leaf deflection (e. g. its slope) and shaft behaviour during operation (e. g. vibrations) must be designed appropriately. It is thinkable to influence that by the support ring contour or the material properties or geometry of the leaf layers. The results have shown that the present PALS is deflected very fast while differential pressures are still small. Unexpected wear-in at those operating states must be avoided. Otherwise, clear gaps at other operating points could be the consequence.

Further compressed air experiments at moderate differential pressures will be performed in order to preclude dangerous shaft damage, especially under hot steam conditions. During these tests, primarily the rotational speed dependence of the leakage and the wear behaviour in the case of contact between pressure-deflected leaves and shaft as well as the resulting frictional torque must be evaluated – for both centred and eccentric shaft position.

The occurrence of vibrations only under certain operating conditions suggests an interaction of the leaves with the shaft boundary layer with simultaneously still insufficient damping of the leaves due to the applied pressure difference. Therefore, if shaft rotation has a significant effect on the vibration propensity is also one of the questions on the next test campaigns. Furthermore, it is not completely certain yet if the oscillations are a circumferentially constant phenomenon or if there is any kind of start at certain leaves – analogously to rotating stall at turbomachine blades. However, due to the high complexity of the oscillation system, numerical investigations are necessary, too, in order to be able to make more substantiated statements on this topic.

At the end, it could also be interesting to test possible reasons for seal failure. One of those reasons might be overload at more than design pressure. Effects similar to the so-called “blow-over” at brush seals [11] could potentially be catastrophic for the affected leaves.

4. CONCLUSION

PALS can be confirmed as a technology full of potential for efficient, but also load-adaptive operation. Thereto, very small cold clearance and overlapping design are necessary. The wear-in behaviour as well as unsteady oscillation phenomena require further investigation before industrial steam turbine application.

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